

BASE PARAMETERS OF THE MODULAR PLOW

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Abstract In our republic, in addition to double-layer plows, general-purpose plows are widely used. But these plows are imported from foreign countries, and they do not fully meet the requirements for plowing land in the conditions of our Republic. In addition, their price is high, which leads to an increase in the cost of cultivated agricultural crops. Based on this, the construction scheme of the modular plow designed to perform general work for high-powered wheeled tractors widely used in our Republic was developed and research was conducted to justify its parameters.

Key words: plug, longitudinal distance, module, body, agrotechnics

MATERIAL AND METHODS.

This article presents the results of studies on determining the coverage widths of the developed modular plow and its housings, the longitudinal distance between the housings, and the width and diameter of the base wheel hub.

We determine the coverage width of the plug and its housing according to the following expressions [1]:

$$B = \eta P / (k a_{max})$$

$$b_k \leq 1.2a$$

where η is the coefficient of tractor traction; P - nominal traction force; k - relative resistance of the soil to plowing; a -maximum processing depth.

At present, high-powered tractors belonging to class 4-5 in terms of traction force and nominal traction force of 40-50 kN are used in our Republic [2]. Taking this into account and taking $\eta=0.9$; $k=65$; kPa [3] and $a_{max}=35$ cm according to expressions (1) and (2) for use with them, the widths of the plug and its casing are 1.6- We determine that it should be 2.0 m and 40 cm.

The longitudinal distance between the casings (Fig. 2) was determined on the condition that the deformation zone of the processed casing does not reach the structural elements of the casing located ahead of it, because otherwise the free passage of the soil casing between the casings is not ensured, and as a result, the burial of plant residues depth and completeness, the degree of soil compaction will not be at the required level. It had the following expression:

Figure 1. Structural scheme of the modular plug

Figure 2. Scheme for determining the longitudinal distance between plug bodies.

$$L_1 \geq l_{nv} + l_{nd} + b_k \operatorname{ctg} \delta$$

where the surface of the l_{nv} -body with a plough-turner is forward of the field section: the length of the part of the l_{nd} -body field board that protrudes back from the turner.

The analysis of expressions (3), (4) in the first type of decomposition increases the coverage width of the case by the value of 4, and in the second case decreases it

$l_{nv}=35$ cm; $l_{nd}=15$ cm. $a=35$ cm; $b_k = 0.40$ m; $\delta=50^\circ$; $\alpha_k=30^\circ$; $\varphi_1=30^\circ$; $\varphi_2=40^\circ$ va $\beta_k = 40^\circ$, the calculations made according to expressions (3) and (4) showed that the longitudinal distance between plug bodies intended for general works should not be less than 88 cm .

So, according to the conducted studies, in order for the plow to be aggregated with the TT3-100SP vegetable tractor to plow the land with good quality, the vertical distance from the support surface to the lower suspension points of the suspension device is at least 62 cm, the width and length of the field board - 18 and 33 cm, respectively. , and the longitudinal distance between the bodies should be 77.4 cm.

Wheelbase width and diameter. In order to ensure the required evenness of the driving depth, the depth of submersion of the support wheel into the soil is determined by the following expression, based on the condition that the processing depth does not exceed the permissible value of unevenness:

$$h_o = \sqrt[3]{\frac{9(mgl_1 - R_{xz}l_2 - F_x l_3)^2}{4[q_0(1 + kV^2)]^2 B_k^2 D (l_4 + \mu l_5)^2}}$$

Based on the analysis of this expression, the depth of immersion of the plow base wheel into the soil and, therefore, its walking depth, the uniformity of the weight of the plow, the amount of forces acting on the plow-turning surfaces of its field boards and bodies, the physical and mechanical properties of the soil, the support g It depends on the position, width, diameter and speed of the drive unit

To ensure uniformity of the plowing depth, it is necessary that $h_0 \leq \Delta h$ (where Δh is the permissible size of unevenness of the plowing depth). This can be achieved by correctly choosing the width and diameter of the base wheel of the plug, based on expression (5).

Figure 3 shows the graph of the change of h_0 depending on D , B_k and l_4 . In this case $m=1000$ kg. $R_{XZ}=36 \cdot 10^3$ H. $F_x=6 \cdot 10^3$ H. $q_0 = 1.5 \cdot 10^7$ N. $l_1 = 3.9$ m. $l_2 = 0.5$ m, $l_3 = 0.9$ m and $l_4 = 5.6$ m. $l_5 = 0.15$ m. $KV = 0.08$ c/m² and $m = 0.2$ are accepted [3,4,5].

As can be seen from the graphs presented in Figure 2.7, with the increase in the diameter and width of the base wheel, the value of h_0 decreases and, therefore, the uniformity of the driving depth improves.

According to current agrotechnical requirements [2] $\Delta h = 42$ cm.

Figure 3. Graphs of changes in the depth h_0 of the plow support wheel at different speeds depending on its width (a) and diameter (b)

In order for the depth of the base wheel of the plug to not be more than this value, the width of the base wheel node in Figure 2.7 at a speed of 6-8 km/h should be less than 48.3 cm in diameter from 21.5 cm. should not be.

CONCLUSION

According to the conducted studies, for high-quality plowing of land with a modular plow aggregated with high-power wheeled tractors, the width of the plow and its body is 1.6-2.0 m and 40 cm, respectively, the longitudinal distance between the bodies is at least - 88 cm, and the width of the base wheel hub should not be less than 21.5 cm, and the diameter should not be less than 48.3 cm.

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